

Pengembangan Algoritma Hiper-Heuristik untuk Menyelesaikan Permasalahan Optimasi Penjadwalan Mata Kuliah dan Rute Kendaraan Penjemputan Dosen Terintegrasi

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Bidang riset operasi dan ilmu komputer telah terbukti menjadi solusi efektif dalam mengatasi masalah optimasi kombinatorik termasuk integrasi penjadwalan dan rute kendaraan. Pada sektor kesehatan, transportasi dan logistik, penelitian sebelumnya telah berhasil mengintegrasikan penjadwalan dan rute kendaraan, baik secara sekuensial maupun simultan. Pada topik dunia pendidikan, dikenal tiga topik utama dalam penjadwalan, yaitu penjadwalan mata kuliah, ujian dan sekolah menengah. Sedangkan pada topik rute kendaraan dikenal memiliki banyak varian, dua yang paling dominan yaitu rute kendaraan berkapasitas dan rute kendaraan yang bergantung pada waktu. Namun, menariknya, publikasi terkait integrasi penjadwalan mata kuliah dan rute kendaraan berkapasitas belum pernah ditemukan sebelumnya, padahal kasus tersebut ditemukan pada dunia nyata. Penelitian ini bertujuan mengembangkan model matematis dan algoritma hiper-heuristik yang mampu menyelesaikan masalah optimasi integrasi tersebut. Penelitian ini diharapkan menghasilkan proses penjadwalan mata kuliah dan penentuan rute kendaraan yang lebih efisien, mengurangi biaya transportasi, serta meningkatkan preferensi dosen dan mahasiswa. Temuan penelitian ini diharapkan dapat memberikan kontribusi penting dalam bidang riset operasi dan ilmu komputer untuk mengisi celah pengetahuan terkait integrasi penjadwalan dan rute kendaraan.

Kata kunci: Penjadwalan Mata Kuliah, Rute Kendaraan Berkapasitas, Integrasi, Metaheuristik, Hiper-heuristik

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Development of A Hyper-Heuristic Algorithm for Solving Integrated Course Timetabling and Lecturer Pickup Vehicle Routing Problems

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The field of operations research and computer science has proven to be effective in addressing combinatorial optimization problems, including the integration of scheduling and vehicle routing. In healthcare, transportation, and logistics sectors, previous studies have successfully integrated scheduling and vehicle routing, either sequentially or simultaneously. In education, three primary topics in timetabling are recognized: course timetabling, exam timetabling, and high school timetabling. Meanwhile, the topic of vehicle routing is known to have many variants, with the two most dominant being capacitated vehicle routing and time-dependent vehicle routing. Interestingly, publications related to the integration of course timetabling and capacitated vehicle routing have not been previously discovered, even though such cases exist in real-world scenarios. This research aims to develop a mathematical model and hyperheuristics algorithm to solve the integrated optimization problem. This research is expected to produce a more efficient course timetabling process and vehicle route determination, reduce transportation costs, and enhance preferences for both lecturers and students. The findings of this research are expected to significantly contribute to the fields of operations research and computer science, filling the knowledge gap related to the integration of scheduling and vehicle routing.

Keywords: University course timetabling problem, vehicle routing problem, integration, Heuristics, Metaheuristics, Hyperheuristics

Biography

Dihin Muriyatmoko received the Engineer of Applied Technology and Master of Engineering degrees from Institut Teknologi Sepuluh Nopember (ITS) Surabaya Indonesia in 2012 and 2015. He is still studying for a doctoral degree in Information Systems at ITS Surabaya for 2022-2025. He is also a lecturer and researcher in Informatics Engineering at Universitas Darussalam Gontor, Indonesia. His research interests include mobile applications, game technology, data mining, and combinatorial optimization problems. His email contact is dihin@unida.gontor.ac.id.

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